

Hazard, exposure, fragility, and damage state homogenization of a virtual oil refinery testbed for seismic risk assessment

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A virtual mid-size oil refinery, located in a high-seismicity region of Greece, is offered as a testbed for developing and testing system-level assessment methods due to direct impact from seismic shaking and without considering geohazards, such as liquefaction and surface faulting. Its characterization is offered in a dedicated repository (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11419659>) and it comprises: (a) a comprehensive probabilistic treatment of seismic hazard tied to an open source seismological model; (b) a hazard-consistent set of ground motion records; (c) a full geolocated exposure model with all pertinent critical assets, namely tanks, pressure vessels, process towers, chimneys, equipment-supporting buildings, and a flare; (d) the corresponding record-wise asset demands and summarized fragilities derived via nonlinear dynamic analyses on reduced-order numerical models. Background information is provided on all refinery assets to delineate their role in the refining process. Furthermore, an explicit homogenization of the damage states is proposed, translating them from the asset level to the refinery system level considering the importance of each asset on the overall operational and structural integrity of the refinery. The results can form the basis of any follow-up study that seeks to characterize the effects of cascading failures (fires, explosions), mitigation measures, seismic sequences, and operational constraints on the functionality, risk, and resilience of refining facilities.

KEYWORDS

Crude oil refinery, exposure model, virtual testbed, seismic fragility, system impact

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INTRODUCTION

29 Crude oil refining facilities are essential infrastructure for the seamless functioning of
30 a modern society. Crude oil is extracted at onshore and offshore rigs; it is transported via
31 ships and pipelines to crude oil refineries (upstream part) and is then processed to produce
32 liquid and gaseous fuels (midstream part) that are eventually delivered to customers and
33 consumers (downstream part), as shown in Figure 1. The basis of the oil refining process is
34 founded upon the fact that straight-run distillates cannot be directly consumed as fuel due
35 to the high concentration of impurities they contain, and because the octane and cetane
36 numbers are inappropriate for gasoline and diesel engines, respectively (Ancheyta, 2011).
37 Therefore, numerous complex physical and chemical processes are required to deliver the
38 final products. To do so, an oil refinery consists of a variety of assets that are located within
39 a limited area and interact mainly functionally (as opposed to structurally) as they are
40 interconnected via a dense piping network. Thus, the overall health, resilience, and
41 uninterrupted operation of this complex system significantly depend on the structural
42 integrity of its individual assets. As refineries appear to play an important role within the
43 energy supply chain, strict rules, provisions, and guidelines are in effect to ensure their
44 safety and operability, from the design phase up to everyday operation and maintenance
45 activities. However, past earthquake-triggered Natural-Technological (NaTech) accidents,
46 e.g., the 1964 Niigata and the 1978 Miyagi earthquakes, Japan (Yoshida, 2014), the 1999
47 Kocaeli earthquake, Türkiye (Cruz and Steinberg, 2005; Steinberg and Cruz, 2004), the
48 2003 Tokachi-Oki earthquake, Japan (Hatayama, 2008), the 2010 Bío-Bío offshore
49 earthquake, Chile (Zareian et al., 2012), and the 2011 Great East Japan earthquake
50 (Krausmann and Cruz, 2021), have resulted in devastating consequences for the
51 environment, the economy, and society, thus highlighting the pressing need for more
52 reliable seismic risk estimates in industrial facilities.

53 While the consensus regarding community-critical infrastructures is that their seismic
54 performance assessment shall be carried out on a probabilistic performance basis to account
55 for aleatory and epistemic uncertainties (Cornell and Krawinkler, 2000), research efforts to
56 date are mainly focused on improving the state of knowledge on the seismic performance
57 of individual refinery assets, such as tanks (Bakalis et al., 2017; Bakalis and Karamanos,
58 2021; Korkmaz et al., 2011; Vasquez Munoz and Dolšek, 2023; Vathi and Karamanos,
59 2018), chimneys and process towers (e.g., Karaferis et al., 2022), pressure vessels (e.g.,
60 Karaferis et al., 2023; Wieschollek et al., 2011), building-type structures (Butenweg et al.,
61 2021; Butenweg and Holtschoppen, 2014; Kazantzi et al., 2022), and pipe racks (Bursi et
62 al., 2016; Di Sarno and Karagiannakis, 2020). At the same time, the treatment of oil

63 refineries as integrated systems is rather limited, with mostly parts of the petrochemical
 64 facilities being investigated in an explicit manner (e.g., Farhan and Bousias, 2020; Zhang
 65 et al., 2021), while a limited number of qualitative assessment studies have been also carried
 66 out (Camila et al., 2019; Cozzani et al., 2014; Krausmann et al., 2019). In more recent
 67 studies, associated frameworks to assess the resilience of process plants have been proposed
 68 (Caputo et al., 2020; Corritore et al., 2021; Kalemi et al., 2023).

69
 70 **Figure 1.** The role of oil refineries as a core element in the oil supply chain.

71 If the above is any indication, refineries are complex, and attempting a system-level
 72 study carries a steep initial cost. This is the definition of the case study itself, whose details
 73 often end up mattering more than any attempted further contribution. Such hurdles have
 74 appeared again and again in earthquake engineering. One is reminded of the early Pacific
 75 Earthquake Engineering Research (PEER) Center testbeds that helped jump-start
 76 performance-based earthquake engineering (Porter, 2003), as well as the more recent
 77 example of the Centerville community resilience testbed (Ellingwood et al., 2016) from the
 78 Resilience Center. In the same spirit, we aim to offer a virtual refinery testbed with enough
 79 information to get researchers started on the system-level assessment.

80 Specifically, a comprehensive virtual testbed is established of a typical mid-sized crude
 81 oil refinery located in a highly seismic area in Greece. It comprises all the needed data to
 82 run a quantitative seismic risk assessment up to the level of direct earthquake-induced
 83 damages due to seismic shaking, excluding cascading events (e.g., fire and/or explosion).
 84 It is noted that earthquake-trigger ground failures (e.g., liquefaction, landslide, faulting) are
 85 not considered. The refinery exposure model is developed first, and the critical assets at
 86 risk are identified, offering a deeper understanding of the role of each asset in the refining
 87 process and their interaction. Seismic hazard analysis results for the area of interest are
 88 offered, along with the selection of hazard-consistent records that are utilized to analyze the

89 numerical models of each asset. Seismic fragility curves are extracted and damage states of
90 individual assets are homogenized per their impact at the refinery level to enable a holistic
91 assessment approach. Using these data and results, the basis for enabling the computation
92 of the seismic risk in an oil refinery plant is detailed in the study, providing all the required
93 input and findings thoroughly. The full set of numerical results is offered in the form of
94 spreadsheets at Melissianos et al. (2024). Additional information such as
95 repair/replacement costs, daily revenue, or amount of oil products processed in the facility
96 is not offered as they are very case-specific, and typically not disclosed by operators.

97 Overall, one can employ the data provided as a testbed to apply and evaluate the results
98 of different assessment methodologies, testing the effect of simplifications, formulations,
99 discrepancies of concepts, and assumptions involved in assessing the seismic risk of
100 refineries. Using the data provided, one can extricate oneself from tedious structural
101 modeling and analysis and focus on capturing, for instance, the effect of asset correlation,
102 common cause failures, mitigation measures, and the complex phenomena emanating from
103 initial damage, investigating cascading effects and spread of damage due to loss of
104 containment and subsequent fires. On the other hand, the data offered is not suitable for
105 addressing soil-related effects, e.g., soil-structure interaction or soil-amplification, as the
106 fragilities provided do not incorporate such information.

107 **REFINERY EXPOSURE MODEL**

108 A comprehensive list of the main structures typically encountered in an oil refinery is
109 provided in Table 1. More detail, crude oil (raw material) is imported into the refinery
110 through steel piping, typically buried pipelines of large diameter, and stored in atmospheric
111 liquid storage tanks (Figure 2). Then, crude oil is refined through numerous chemical and
112 physical processes (i.e., atmospheric distillation, isomerization, catalytic hydrotreating,
113 polymerization and alkylation, fluid catalytic cracking, solvent deasphalting, coking, etc.)
114 in the refining units, which are the core of the facility and include a variety of structures
115 and mechanical equipment. Liquids and gasses are continuously circulated in the refining
116 units via a dense steel piping network (Figure 7). Processes, such as fluid catalytic cracking
117 and vacuum distillation take place at process towers [Figure 5(a)]. Some other processes,
118 such as heat transfer, take place in mechanical equipment, nested and/or supported by
119 reinforced concrete (RC) and/or steel buildings (Figure 4). The gases or liquids under
120 pressure required for the refining processes are stored in pressure vessels [Figure 3(b),(c)].
121 Vapors collected in a closed safety system are disposed of by burning at the refinery flare
122 [Figure 5(c)]. Gaseous wastes are released in the air via steel and/or RC chimneys [Figure

123 5(a),(b)]. Numerous electrical substations [Figure 6(c)], which are scattered throughout the
 124 refinery, provide the necessary electrical power. Intermediate products of the refining
 125 process, such as slope oil, are stored in atmospheric liquid storage tanks (Figure 2). The
 126 final liquid products (marine oil, diesel, gasoline, jet oil, naphtha, asphalt, lubricants, etc.)
 127 are stored in atmospheric tanks (Figure 2), while gases (propane, butane, etc.) in spherical
 128 pressure tanks [Figure 3(a)]. Fuel products are exported and supplied to customers via (1)
 129 onshore pipelines in the case of very large consumers, such as an airport, (2) road or rail
 130 trucks that are loaded at stations [Figure 6(a)] or (3) ships that moor at piers equipped with
 131 dense piping [Figure 6(b)]. Additional structures that are encountered in a refinery comprise
 132 control rooms, auxiliary and administrative buildings, cooling towers, etc.

133 **Table 1.** List of refinery structures.

Structure	Function
Liquid storage tanks	Storage of liquid products (crude oil, gasoline, naphtha, diesel, marine oil, jet oil, etc.) [Figure 2]
Pressure vessels	Spherical pressure vessels for storage of final gaseous products (butane, propane, etc.) [Figure 3(a)]
Equipment-supporting buildings	Steel [Figure 4(a)] and/or Reinforced Concrete (RC) [Figure 4(b)] buildings that support mechanical equipment and machinery (pressure vessels, heat exchangers, converters, pumps, electrical equipment, etc.)
Process towers	High-rise cylindrical steel stacks [Figure 5(a)], where physical or chemical processing takes place (e.g., fluid catalytic cracking, distillation, alkylation, etc.)
Chimneys	Steel [Figure 5(b)] and RC high-rise stacks for the release of gaseous wastes
Pressure vessels	Cylindrical horizontal and vertical pressure vessels for storage of gases used in the refining process [Figure 3(b),(c)]
Flare	Flammable gases and vapors are transported to the top of the high-rise steel lattice tower to be combusted [Figure 5(c)]
Other structures	Control rooms, auxiliary and administrative buildings, truck-loading station [Figure 6(a)], pier [Figure 6(b)], electrical substations [Figure 6(c)], cooling towers
Piping	Dense network of buried, above-ground [Figure 7(a)], and rack-supported [Figure 7(b)] steel piping for oil and gas circulation within the facility

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135

136 **Figure 2.** Atmospheric liquid-storage steel tanks.

(a)

(b)

(c)

137 **Figure 3.** Steel pressure vessels: (a) spherical, (b) horizontal, and (c) vertical.

(a)

(b)

138 **Figure 4.** (a) Steel and (b) RC equipment-supporting buildings in refining units.

(a)

(b)

(c)

139 **Figure 5.** High-rise stacks: (a) process tower, (b) steel chimney, (c) flare.

(a)

(b)

(c)

140 **Figure 6.** Other structures: (a) truck-loading station, (b) pier, (c) electrical substation.

(a)

(b)

141 **Figure 7.** Steel piping: (a) above-ground, (b) rack-supported.

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VIRTUAL REFINERY TESTBED

143 A typical mid-size refinery, in terms of functionality and production, is offered as the
 144 VASEL virtual testbed. The refinery plan view is illustrated in Figure 8, covering an area
 145 of 1850m × 1250m. The structures outside the refining unit areas are listed in Table 2,
 146 while the structures in the four refining unit areas are listed in Table 3. The exact location
 147 of each asset within the refinery stems from the balance between operational optimization
 148 and safety provisions (Khor and Elkamel, 2010; Pinto et al., 2000). Some basic principles
 149 are the following: (1) the liquid storage tanks cover most of the area and surround the
 150 sensitive assets of the facility, namely the refining units, (2) the spherical pressure vessels
 151 are located on the seaside or close to a mountain and in any case on the opposite direction
 152 of a populated area to minimize the effects in case of failure or accident (e.g., plumes,
 153 fireballs, heat radiation) to the facility or the surrounding area, and (3) the main refinery
 154 flare is typically located outside the refining units area.

155 **Table 2.** Number of individual refinery structures considered in the exposure model (Figure 8)
 156 [“No.” denotes the number of structures].

Structure	No.	Structure	No.	Structure	No.
Gasoline tank	6	Naphtha tank	6	Liquid asphalt tank	4
Fuel oil tank	2	Crude oil tank	12	Water tank	2
Marine diesel oil tank	8	Diesel tank	4	Flare	1
Jet A-1 tank	8	Slop oil tank	2	Spherical pressure vessel	4

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Figure 8. Exposure model: Plan view of the case study oil refinery

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Table 3. Aggregate number of structures in the four refining unit areas considered in the exposure model (Figure 8) [“No.” denotes the number of structures].

Structure	No.	Structure	No.	Structure	No.
1-story RC building	3	Process tower	5	Horizontal pressure vessel	8
2-story RC building	17	30m steel chimney	3	Vertical pressure vessel type CL1	12
4-story RC building	7	80m steel chimney	1	Vertical pressure vessel type CL2	8
1-story steel building	10	RC chimney	1		
2-story steel building	9				

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It should be noted that some of the structures listed in Table 1 were not explicitly considered in the analysis, thus missing from Tables 2 and 3, as discussed below:

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- Control rooms are typically heavily oversized to additionally serve as bunkers in case of an accident, thus seismic-induced damages are unlikely.
- Auxiliary and administrative buildings, as well as truck loading stations, are designed with increased safety factors. The potential damage or partial failure of these structures is not anticipated to contribute to a NaTech event.

- 169 • Piers of marine oil terminals are vulnerable primarily to seismic-induced permanent
170 ground displacements, such as those caused by liquefaction (Goel, 2022; Huang and
171 Han, 2020), and are thus not examined herein.
- 172 • Buried steel piping mainly consists of straight segments, that may be damaged due to
173 transient ground displacements caused by seismic wave propagation under specific
174 circumstances related to the soil stratigraphy (e.g., Psyrras et al., 2019; Psyrras and
175 Sextos, 2018). Uniform soil conditions have been assumed for the purpose of the testbed
176 and consequently the failure of buried pipes due to seismic wave propagation has been
177 excluded from the scope of work. It should be noted that the buried piping network of
178 the refinery is not directly analogous to an urban gas distribution network since the latter
179 extends over a greater (city-level) area with varying geological conditions and, thus is
180 more vulnerable to seismic-induced permanent and transient ground displacements (e.g.,
181 Farahani et al., 2020; Kurtuluş, 2011; O'Rourke et al., 2014).
- 182 • Above-ground piping is typically attached to sleepers with or without pendulum-type
183 connectors, while expansion joints, U-type pipe loops, elbows, and bends provide the
184 required flexibility for piping thermal expansion and contraction. The two latter
185 conditions tend to be more prevalent where pipe damage is concerned. These
186 configurations along with the piping's inherent flexibility allow the piping system to
187 undergo slight transverse and longitudinal displacements, thus at most times safely
188 accommodating those imposed by the ground shaking.

189 It is worth mentioning that although aspects, such as (1) structural interconnectivity
190 (e.g., Zhang et al., 2021), (2) local failures of the piping systems, for example, pipe-to-tank
191 connections (O'Rourke et al., 2008; Vathi et al., 2017), (3) failure of piping components
192 (e.g., Hosseini et al., 2020), and (4) global failure of the piping systems (e.g., Bursi et al.,
193 2015) are not considered in our analysis, their impact on the seismic risk is expected to be
194 nontrivial and needs to be further investigated. The same applies for the pipe racks, which
195 are open-frame steel (non-building) structures with versatile configuration (Xu et al., 2020).
196 It has been identified after past earthquake events that pipe racks may not be the most
197 vulnerable structures (Krausmann et al., 2010; Paolacci et al., 2012). Still, the potentially
198 critical pipe racks (based on engineering judgment and expert opinion) should be accounted
199 for in a case-specific study. The interested reader may find more information in recent
200 studies (e.g., Bedair, 2015; di Sarno and Karagiannakis, 2020a, 2020b) that tried to shed
201 more light on the seismic performance of pipe racks. Finally, the power system (e.g.,
202 Brennan and Koliou, 2021; Koliou et al., 2013; Oliveto and Reinhorn, 2018; Xie et al.,

203 2019), the water and steam distribution network (e.g., Vathi et al., 2017), and transportation
204 networks and their interconnectivity with the refinery structures are not included in the
205 exposure model.

206

SEISMIC HAZARD

207 The examined refinery is assumed to be located within a major industrial area, in the
208 west of Athens, Greece (Figure 9). The OpenQuake engine (Pagani et al., 2014), developed
209 by the Global Earthquake Model Foundation, was employed to compute the seismic hazard
210 in the area of interest. The hazard calculations were based on the results of the 2013
211 European Seismic Hazard Model (Woessner et al., 2015), for simplicity employing only
212 the area source model and the Ground Motion Prediction Equation of Boore and Atkinson
213 (2008) for the site at longitude 23.507 and latitude 38.04. It is noted the seismic hazard at
214 the area of interest is dominated by the Corinth Gulf faults to the south-southwest, with
215 shallow crustal events having been recorded within a few kilometers of the site. The
216 Hellenic Arc subduction zone is located much further to the south and, although it can
217 produce larger magnitude events, the closest point to the site of interest is at such a
218 horizontal distance (~55km) and depth (~80km) that the Arc's contribution to the
219 short/moderate period hazard is insignificant. For instance, a highly rare “nearby” M8 event
220 on the Hellenic Arc would result in median peak ground accelerations (PGAs) of the order
221 of 0.02–0.04g, when the 475-year value is an order of magnitude higher at 0.32g and the
222 2475 year value reaching 0.60g (Danciu et al. 2021, Pitilakis et al. 2024). Thus, only the
223 shallow crustal events are considered henceforth.

224

225 **Figure 9.** Case study area: A major industrial area (marked with a red rectangle) located west of
226 Athens, Greece.

227

228 The seismic intensity measure (IM) serves as an interface variable between seismic
229 hazard and structural analysis and should be a good predictor of the Engineering Demand
Parameter (EDP) utilized for the assets under investigation (Kohrangi et al., 2023; Luco

230 and Cornell, 2007). To satisfy this requirement for the various structural typologies that are
231 encountered in an oil refinery, two scalar IMs were employed, namely the peak ground
232 acceleration (*PGA*) and the average spectral acceleration [*AvgS_a* (Cordova et al., 2000;
233 Eads et al., 2015; Kazantzi and Vamvatsikos, 2015; Vamvatsikos and Cornell, 2005)]. *PGA*
234 is an asset-agnostic IM (e.g., Karaferis et al., 2022) and was defined herein as the geometric
235 mean of the *PGA* values in the two horizontal components of the utilized recorded ground
236 motion records. *AvgS_a* is a (moderately) asset-aware IM (e.g., Karaferis et al., 2022) and
237 is defined herein as the geometric mean of the spectral accelerations evaluated for both
238 principal horizontal directions within a range of periods. The selected range of periods
239 spans from 0.1s to 1.0s in increments of 0.1s. The adopted period range accounts for the
240 vibration periods that are encountered in the majority of the oil refinery structures. It should
241 be underlined that, in general, the optimum—in terms of efficiency—spectral-based IM for
242 each structure is different from the one that was considered herein. However, for a portfolio
243 of structures with considerably different geometry and dynamic characteristics, as in the
244 case of a refinery plant, using more structure-specific IMs [e.g., $S_a(T_1)$] for each one of the
245 considered assets would have resulted in a rather complex and impractical risk assessment
246 framework for the entire facility. In this case, event-based Probabilistic Seismic Hazard
247 Analysis involving cross-correlated hazard products would be required, involving
248 correlation relationships among the different IMs (or more accurately the IM residuals per
249 Ground Motion Prediction Equation), thus introducing unnecessary complexity.

250 A set of 30 hazard-consistent natural ground motion records was selected for estimating
251 the structural demands through response-history analysis. The ground motion records were
252 both non-pulse-like and non-long-duration, and were selected from the NGA-West2
253 database (Ancheta et al., 2013) using the Conditional Spectrum (CS)-based method
254 reported by Kohrangi et al. (2017, 2018). The set of records corresponds to a probability of
255 exceedance equal to 2% in 50 years (see site hazard curve in Figure 10) that best matches
256 with the CS target (see CS-selected ground motion set in Figure 10). More details on the
257 process of selecting the ground motion records are available by Bakalis et al. (2018) and
258 Karaferis et al. (2022). In general, to achieve near-optimal hazard consistency, one would
259 require multiple such sets of ground motions selected to correspond to the spectral targets
260 at different levels of each IM. Still, a single hazard-consistent set selected at a critical
261 intensity level of a good IM is typically a good enough approximation (Kohrangi et al.,
262 2020). It is noted that uniform soil conditions were assumed throughout the limited footprint
263 (approximately 1.8km × 1.2km) of the case-study refinery facility, allowing to neglect any

264 kind of ground motion spatial variability. Thus, each ground motion record was applied as
 265 is to all refinery assets.

266
 267 **Figure 10.** (Left) Hazard Curve: mean annual frequency of exceeding $AvgS_a$ values; (Right) CS-
 268 selected ground motion set.

269 FRAGILITY ANALYSIS BACKGROUND

270 The typical path for assessing the seismic risk of a structure or infrastructure involves
 271 the evaluation of its seismic fragility, which is essentially a metric of the susceptibility of
 272 the structure to seismic damage. The computation of the analytical fragility curves is a well-
 273 established process (Bakalis and Vamvatsikos, 2018; Baker, 2015; Chatzidaki and
 274 Vamvatsikos, 2021; Dymiotis et al., 1999; Kazantzi et al., 2011; Kwon and Elnashai, 2006;
 275 Silva et al., 2019). The formal definition of fragility is as follows:

$$F_{LS}(IM) = P[LS \text{ violated} | IM] = P[D > C_{LS} | IM] \quad (1)$$

276 where F_{LS} is the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of its argument, D is the EDP
 277 demand and C_{LS} is the EDP capacity threshold paired to a specific Limit State (LS). The
 278 exceedance of the EDP capacity threshold triggers the LS violation and brings the structure
 279 into a higher damage state. It is noted that structure-specific damage states are denoted in
 280 this study as “ds” to make an essential distinction between them and the global ones
 281 referring to the entire facility, denoted as “DS”. The pairing between structure-specific “ds”
 282 and global “DS” (termed “homogenization” of damage states) is offered later in the study.
 283 It is noted that the use of uppercase and lowercase letters for the damage states only serves
 284 to distinguish the refinery- and asset-level damage states, respectively.

285 In an attempt to strike a balance between accuracy and reduced computational effort
 286 (Fragiadakis et al., 2015), the data required to generate fragility functions rely on
 287 Incremental Dynamic Analysis [IDA (Vamvatsikos and Cornell, 2002, 2005)] of reduced-
 288 order numerical models. The models were developed in the open-source OpenSees platform

289 (McKenna and Fenves, 2000) and were subjected to the selected set of ground motion
 290 records.

291 REFINERY ASSETS, DAMAGE STATES, AND STRUCTURAL 292 MODELS

293 *Liquid storage tanks*

294 Atmospheric liquid storage tanks are upright cylindrical thin-walled steel structures
 295 used to store liquid fuel products. Tanks sit on a very stiff reinforced concrete foundation
 296 and are either anchored to it, typically in the case of high aspect-ratio tanks, or unanchored,
 297 in the case of low/moderate aspect-ratio tanks. A set of tanks is considered in the examined
 298 refinery, containing raw material (i.e., crude oil), intermediate products (e.g., slope oil), and
 299 final products (e.g., kerosene, marine oil, etc.), as presented in Table 2. The considered
 300 tanks are listed in Table 4, where tanks TK-2 through TK-10 are unanchored (no physical
 301 connection between the structure and its foundation), while tanks TK-13 through TK-16
 302 are anchored (anchor bolts connect the tank shell to the foundation).

303 **Table 4.** List of liquid storage tanks (ρ_f : product density).

	ID	Product	ρ_f (kg/m ³)		ID	Product	ρ_f (kg/m ³)
Unanchored tanks	TK-2	Gasoline	750 ⁽¹⁾	Anchored tanks	TK-13	Slop oil	900
	TK-3	Fuel oil	900		TK-14	Liquid asphalt	960
	TK-5	Marine diesel oil	820 ⁽³⁾		TK-15	Water	1000
	TK-6	Jet A-1	820 ⁽⁴⁾		TK-16	Liquid asphalt	960
	TK-8	Naphtha	760				
	TK-9	Crude oil	890 ⁽⁵⁾				
	TK-10	Diesel	845 ⁽²⁾				

Product density references: ⁽¹⁾ EN 228:2012+A1:2017 Automotive fuels. Unleaded petrol. Requirements and test methods, ⁽²⁾ EN 590:2023 Automotive fuels – Diesel – Requirements and test methods, ⁽³⁾ ISO 8217 “Petroleum Products – Fuel (class F)”, ⁽⁴⁾ IATA Guidance Material (Kerosene Type), NATO Code F-35, ⁽⁵⁾ ISO 12185:1996 Crude Oil and Petroleum Products - Determination of Density - Oscillating U-Tube Method

304 The tanks were numerically analyzed by employing the reduced-order model developed
 305 by Bakalis et al. (2017), which is capable of capturing not only the response of tanks
 306 supported by anchor straps but also the uplift mechanism of unanchored ones. The EDPs
 307 that were employed to monitor structural performance, along with their corresponding
 308 failure modes are (Bakalis et al., 2017): (a) the base plate plastic rotation (base plate damage
 309 at the wall-to-base connection), (b) the yielding or fracture of the anchor bolts (anchorage
 310 failure), (c) the maximum convective wave height of the freeboard (sloshing damage to
 311 upper shell course), and (d) the meridional shell stress (elephant’s foot buckling). The four
 312 DSs considered for the anchored and the unanchored tanks are summarized in Table 5 along
 313 the associated EDPs, with consequences ranging from no damage to loss of containment.

314 While damage states per individual component (a)-(d) are sequential (e.g., minor versus
 315 major damage to the upper shell course), the four overall damage states are nonsequential
 316 (Bakalis, et al., 2017) and to some extent “simultaneous” per FEMA P-58 parlance,
 317 implying that a tank may progress directly to a severe damage state without necessarily
 318 sustaining earlier and lower damage associated with a less severe state.

319 **Table 5.** Liquid storage tank: Damage state classification and associated EDPs.

Tank	DS	Attainment of DS when	EDP
Anchored	ds0	—	
	ds1	Minor damage to upper shell course OR Anchorage bolt yielding	Sloshing wave height Anchorage displacement
	ds2	Major damage to upper shell course OR Anchorage bolt fracture OR Minor base plate failure	Sloshing wave height Anchorage displacement Base plate plastic rotation
	ds3	Elephant’s foot buckling OR Major base plate failure	Meridional shell stress Base plate plastic rotation
Unanchored	ds0	—	
	ds1	Minor damage to upper shell course	Sloshing wave height
	ds2	Major damage to upper shell course OR Minor base plate failure	Sloshing wave height Base plate plastic rotation
	ds3	Elephant’s foot buckling OR Major base plate failure	Meridional shell stress Base plate plastic rotation

320 The amount of fuel that is stored in liquid storage tanks is a governing parameter
 321 concerning their seismic response (Bakalis, et al., 2017); it is typically expressed through
 322 the fill ratio *FR*, i.e., the ratio of the liquid height to the tank shell height (Bakalis, et al.,
 323 2017). Three indicative fill ratios are presented herein, namely 0.35, 0.65, and 0.95,
 324 featuring the cases of a rather empty tank, a moderately filled one, and a near-full one,
 325 respectively. Owing to the above, each fill ratio corresponds to a different structural
 326 response and behavior, and consequently, a separate set of data is included in the dedicated
 327 repository. The effect of *FR* is presented indicatively for the fuel tank TK-3 in Figure 11 in
 328 terms of fragility curves, revealing that the more liquid contained in the tank, the more
 329 vulnerable it becomes.

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Figure 11. TK-3 fuel oil tank: Empirical-CDF fragility curves for different fill ratios.

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Equipment-supporting buildings

333

Various mechanical equipment, such as heat exchangers, vessels, reactors, etc., are installed in building-type structures that are located within the refining unit areas. These assets are either steel or reinforced concrete (RC) open-frame structures (Figure 4), and typically are heavily overdesigned for fire-proofing. Five typical buildings are examined herein, namely a 1-story RC building (ID: RC1), a 2-story RC building (ID: RC2), a 4-story RC building (ID: RC3), a 1-story steel building (ID: ST1), and a 2-story steel building (ID: ST2), which were adopted from the study of Kazantzi et al. (2022). More details on the geometry and dynamic properties of the structures, as well as the properties of the supporting equipment, are provided in the repository.

342

Reduced-order numerical models were developed with elastic beam-column elements and by assigning a rigid diaphragm at the floor levels. Kazantzi et al. (2022) introduced four distinct global DSs with increased severity to assess the seismic performance of these building-type assets. Different DSs were considered for (i) drift-sensitive structural (e.g., columns) and non-structural components (e.g., piping spanning across the building) in Table 6 and (ii) acceleration-sensitive components (e.g., reactors, exchangers, etc.) in Table 7. The corresponding DSs are sequential per component, but they are potentially nonsequential at the global level, as some critical equipment may fail catastrophically before the structure attains earlier damage states. In more detail, the interstory drift demands were checked against different drift limits for accessing the seismic performance of the drift-sensitive components, while the seismic acceleration demands on the anchorage points of the acceleration-sensitive components were checked against the corresponding acceleration capacity value (evaluated as the design capacity allowing for an increase due to overstrength). The latter were assigned different importance classes (ICs) to reflect mainly their significance in the refining process and the severity of the consequences in

356

357 case of a potential failure. Consequently, anchorage failure of the acceleration-sensitive
 358 non-structural components that belong to a different IC signifies the attainment of a
 359 different damage state.

360 **Table 6.** Equipment-supporting building: DS classification and associated EDPs for drift-sensitive
 361 structural and non-structural components [adapted from (Kazantzi et al., 2022)].

DS	Attainment of DS when	EDP
ds0	—	—
ds1	Exceedance of interstory drift limit associated with slight damage	Interstory drift ratio
ds2	Exceedance of interstory drift limit associated with moderate damage OR Damage to vertical piping spanning across different stories	Interstory drift ratio
ds3	Exceedance of interstory drift limit associated with near-collapse	Interstory drift ratio

362 **Table 7.** Equipment-supporting building: DS classification and associated EDPs for acceleration-
 363 sensitive non-structural components (IC I: low importance equipment, IC II: medium importance
 364 equipment, IC III: high importance equipment) [adapted from (Kazantzi et al., 2022)].

DS	Attainment of DS when	EDP
ds0	—	—
ds1	Anchorage failure of at least one component in IC I	Peak component acceleration
ds2	Anchorage failure of at least one component in IC II	Peak component acceleration
ds3	Anchorage failure of at least one component in IC III	Peak component acceleration

365 The fragility curves for each building that are provided in the repository have been
 366 derived using the “combined component approach” of Kazantzi et al. (2022), tracking
 367 damage states per each individual component and employing the correspondence of Table
 368 6 and Table 7 to translate local damage states reached into a global DS. Some critical
 369 remarks for these curves are the following: (i) drift-sensitive structural and non-structural
 370 components are not critical for the seismic performance of the equipment-supporting
 371 buildings, since the attainment of all the considered DS due to the damages in the drift-
 372 sensitive elements occurs at significantly higher IM levels compared to the acceleration-
 373 sensitive non-structural components; (ii) the fragility curve of a building associated with a
 374 certain DS does not necessarily coincide with the fragility curve of the most vulnerable
 375 component belonging to the importance class paired with this DS per Table 7; (iii) the
 376 “combined component” fragility curve denotes the probability of exceeding the
 377 acceleration capacity of any component associated with a specific importance class,
 378 regardless of its location in the floor plan and its elevation. The empirical-CDF fragility
 379 curves of the acceleration-sensitive non-structural components for the RC and ST buildings
 380 are illustrated in Figure 12. It is observed that the most severe DS3 occurs before DS1 and
 381 DS2 for RC1 and RC2 buildings. The latter is attributed to the exceedance of the capacity
 382 in many IC III (high importance) equipment, leading to early failure.

383
384 **Figure 12.** RC1-3 and ST1-2 buildings: Empirical-CDF fragility curves.

385 *Process tower*

386 Process towers are tall thin-walled steel structures, where core processes of the refining
 387 chain take place, such as atmospheric and vacuum distillation, alkylation, etc. under various
 388 levels of internal pressure and temperature. These towers are fixed-based self-supporting
 389 slender columns [Figure 5(a)]. A 30 m high acid settler with an internal diameter equal to
 390 2.6 m is examined, whose geometry and material properties are detailed in the repository.
 391 A reduced-order lumped mass numerical model was developed, consisting of concentrated
 392 masses at critical elevations along the tower height, connected with elastic beam-column
 393 elements. More details on the structure and its modeling can be found in Karaferis et al.
 394 (2022). Similarly to previous cases, DSs were defined to be sequential per component but
 395 potentially nonsequential globally (or “simultaneous” per FEMA P-58), and they were
 396 considered to assess both the operational and the structural seismic performance of the
 397 process tower (Table 8), focusing on the piping and the shell.

398 **Table 8.** Process tower: Damage state classification and associated EDPs.

DS	Attainment of DS when	EDP
ds0	—	—
ds1	Damage to connected piping	Top drift
ds2	Local buckling of shell	Shell stress-state

399 The empirical-CDF fragility curves of the process tower are presented in Figure 13. By
400 inspecting this figure, it can be inferred that for low to moderate earthquake intensity levels
401 up to 0.4g the probability of structural damage is insignificant, while for higher levels, there
402 is a non-negligible probability for the tower to see some piping damage (ds1) and lose its
403 operational integrity, without necessarily risking structural collapse (ds2).

404
405 **Figure 13.** Process tower: Empirical-CDF fragility curves.

406 *Chimneys*

407 Chimneys are tall hollow tubular structures used for the disposal of gaseous wastes from
408 the refining process. From a structural point of view, chimneys are essentially self-
409 supporting vertical cantilever beams, which are primarily vulnerable to wind hazard. Still,
410 seismic-related damage to a chimney can occur, especially at the more vulnerable base, and
411 it is expected to obstruct the refining process.

412 Three typical chimneys are examined in the VASEL testbed, i.e., a 30m and an 80m
413 high steel chimney [Figure 5(b)] as well as an 87m high RC chimney. These structures have
414 been thoroughly studied by Karaferis et al. (2022) and more details on their geometry and
415 material properties are given in the corresponding spreadsheets in the repository. The
416 chimneys were numerically analyzed using a reduced-order lumped mass model, similar to
417 the one utilized for the process tower. An elastic model was employed for the steel
418 chimneys. For the case of the RC chimney, the elements connecting the concentrated
419 masses were defined as non-linear forced-based beam-column fiber section elements to
420 account for the steel reinforcement and the concrete material properties. To capture material
421 nonlinearity, the Mander et al. (1988) stress-strain model was employed for concrete, while
422 an elastic-hardening model with 1% post-hardening stiffness ratio and bounded ductility
423 was used for the reinforcing steel.

424 Four distinct DSs were defined to evaluate the potential damage to the connected piping,
 425 the liner, and to assess the stability of the structure itself. Damage is sequential per
 426 component, but nonsequential globally. The DS classification and capacity thresholds for
 427 the steel and RC chimneys are listed in Table 9. The obtained empirical-CDF fragility
 428 curves are shown in Figure 14, where for the steel chimneys we observe that the taller one
 429 is more susceptible to both operational disruption (attainment of ds1) and structural damage
 430 (attainment of ds2 or ds3), while in both cases the damage states are sequential. The RC
 431 chimney has a low probability of catastrophic failure (i.e., reaching ds3 due to cross-section
 432 failure) but is more prone to non-structural and minor structural damages, which could
 433 undermine its operational continuity.

434 **Table 9.** Steel chimney: DS classification and associated EDPs.

Chimney	DS	Attainment of DS when	EDP
Steel	ds0	—	—
	ds1	Damage to connected piping	Top drift
	ds2	Damage to liner	Interstory drift
	ds3	Local buckling of shell	Shell stress-state
RC	ds0	—	—
	ds1	Damage to connected piping	Top drift
	ds2	Damage to liner or cross-section yielding	Interstory drift or cross-sectional moment
	ds3	Cross-section failure	Cross-sectional moment

435

436

437 **Figure 14.** Chimneys: Empirical-CDF fragility curves.

438 *Flare*

439 The main flare [Figure 5(c)] is the landmark structure in each oil refinery. It is device
 440 for the combustion of regulated vent steams and non-routine emissions resulting from leaks,
 441 purges, emergency releases, etc. from the from the refining process (RTI International,

442 2015). A network of piping and equipment collects these wastes and transports them to the
 443 top of the flare stack to be burned (Bahadori, 2014). From a structural point of view, the
 444 flare stack is typically a steel lattice tower that supports the vertical piping and the
 445 combustion device at the top of the tower. If its operation is disturbed or its structural
 446 integrity is endangered due to the occurrence of an earthquake event, the consequences may
 447 be far from trivial. This is because in the case of low damage the refining process may be
 448 disrupted, while in the case of major damage, fire or explosion can occur due to the
 449 hazardous gasses transported within the piping.

450 A 67.4 m high flare stack is examined for the testbed refinery, consisting of a steel
 451 lattice tower with members (legs, diagonals, horizontal) made of circular hollow sections.
 452 The structure has been thoroughly investigated by Karaferis et al. (2022) and more details
 453 on the geometry and the assumed material properties are provided in the repository. A
 454 reduced-order numerical model was developed to analyze the structure. All members were
 455 modeled using non-linear force-based beam-column elements with fiber sections, following
 456 the modeling technique for steel lattice towers proposed by Billionis et al. (2022).

457 Four distinct damage states (Table 10) were defined to examine the potential damage
 458 to mechanical equipment due to excessive top displacement of the tower, to the vertical
 459 piping spanning along the tower height due to excessive intersegment drift, and to the tower
 460 itself due to tensile or buckling failure of a member causing catastrophic failure of the
 461 structure. Damage states are sequential per component, but nonsequential globally. The
 462 empirical-CDF fragility curves obtained from the analysis are depicted in Figure 15 for
 463 both IMs that are considered in the present study. It can be inferred that the most critical
 464 state is ds3 across the investigated *IM* range, implying that the potential for structural failure
 465 is much higher than the potential for operational damages that are depicted through ds1 and
 466 ds2. This is an outcome that can be partially attributed to the high stiffness of the tower,
 467 which makes it difficult to reach the top and intersegment limits adopted as capacity
 468 thresholds for ds1 and ds2, respectively, as well as to the limited redundancy of the flare
 469 against individual member failures.

470 **Table 10.** Flare: Damage state classification and associated EDPs.

DS	Attainment of DS when	EDP
ds0	—	—
ds1	Damage to equipment	Top drift
ds2	Damage to vertical piping	Intersegment drift
ds3	Tensile or buckling structural member failure	Forces and moments of structural members

471

472
473 **Figure 15.** Flare: Empirical-CDF fragility curves.

474 *Spherical Pressure Vessels*

475 Spherical pressure vessels [Figure 3(a)] are used in refineries for the storage of liquefied
476 petroleum gasses, such as propane, butane, butadiene, isobutylene, and mixtures thereof.
477 These steel spherical vessels are elevated and supported by steel legs of circular hollow
478 sections either equipped with X-bracing or not. Spherical vessels are vulnerable to
479 earthquake-induced damages due to the elevated concentrated mass, especially when fully
480 filled, as revealed in the aftermath of past seismic events [e.g., Li et al. (2015)].

481 The considered tank consists of a 20.22 m diameter sphere that is supported by 12
482 columns with X-bracing and the height to the equator is equal to 13.63 m (Moschonas et
483 al., 2014), while more details on the geometry and the material properties used can be found
484 in the repository. The reduced-order numerical model of Karaferis et al. (2023) was
485 employed to analyze the structure. In more detail, the spherical vessel is simplified to two
486 concentrated masses (Karamanos et al., 2006), i.e., the impulsive and the convective
487 components of the fluid mass, the former also containing the mass of the shell. Both are
488 located at the center of the sphere, and connected to the supporting columns via elastic
489 springs and rigid links. The columns are discretized into nonlinear beam-column elements
490 and the braces are modeled with nonlinear truss elements. The basic assumptions of the
491 modeling approach are (i) the flexibility of the vessel is ignored since any earthquake-
492 induced deformations are anticipated to be much lower than those of the supporting system,
493 (ii) the shell is not expected to fail before the supporting system, and (iii) the welded
494 connections of the vessel to the columns have sufficient strength. Three sequential damage
495 states were defined to evaluate the structural damage of the tank. The considered EDP is
496 the horizontal displacement (d_v) at the center of the sphere (location of the impulsive mass).
497 The damage state classification and capacity thresholds (the latter being case-specific and
498 defined via pushover analysis) are listed in Table 11.

499
500

Table 11. Spherical pressure vessels: Damage state classification and associated EDPs [adapted from Karaferis et al. (2023)].

DS	Attainment of DS when	EDP
ds0	—	—
ds1	First yielding of any brace in tension	$d_v \geq 0.063$ m
ds2	Yielding of more than 50% of braces in tension	$d_v \geq 0.091$ m
ds3	Fracture of any brace	$d_v \geq 0.171$ m

501 The amount of gas that is stored in the spherical vessel is expressed by the fill ratio,
502 akin to the liquid storage tanks, and determines their seismic response. A range of fill ratios
503 was considered in the study, from 0.35 to 0.95 with an increment of 0.10. Essentially, each
504 fill ratio results in a different structure in terms of its dynamic response subject to an
505 earthquake excitation. The effect of the fill ratio (FR) on seismic fragility curves is
506 showcased indicatively in Figure 16 for the three values of 0.35, 0.65, and 0.95,
507 corresponding to a rather empty, a half-filled, and an almost-filled tank, respectively.
508 Results for these fill ratios are offered in the repository. It is observed, as expected, that
509 spherical pressure vessels with lower fill ratios are less fragile.

510
511
512

Figure 16. Spherical pressure vessels: Ensemble empirical-CDF fragility curves for different fill ratios.

513 *Cylindrical Pressure Vessels*

514 Numerous horizontal and vertical pressure vessels [Figure 3(b),(c)] are scattered
515 throughout the refining units for storing the various liquids and gasses that are used in the
516 refining process at various temperatures and pressures. Two types of vessels are examined
517 for the VASEL testbed: (a) horizontal cylindrical vessels with steel saddles and vertical
518 rigid supports and (b) vertical cylindrical vessels supported by skirts. These assets have
519 been thoroughly investigated and analyzed by the research team of the EU-funded research
520 project “PEC – Post-Emergency, Multi-Hazard Health Risk Assessment in Chemical
521 Disasters” and reported in deliverable D.B.1 “Definition of the structural models and
522 seismic fragility analysis techniques available for the specific case study”. The published

523 fragility curves are adopted herein without developing any additional numerical models or
 524 undertaking any further analyses. It should be noted that the PEC researchers have carried
 525 out their analysis using the *PGA* as an IM. Since $AvgS_a$ is also adopted herein, an IM
 526 transformation process was performed through disaggregation of the given fragility curves,
 527 using the method presented by Karaferis and Vamvatsikos (2022) to produce fragility
 528 curves for $AvgS_a$ as the IM.

529 Two categories of vertical pressure vessels were examined by the PEC researchers
 530 based on the height-over-diameter ratio (H/R), namely, type CL1 for $4 \leq H/R \leq 7$ and
 531 type CL2 for $7 < H/R \leq 11$. Following an analysis of the base connection resistance and
 532 potential damage to the connected piping due to the vessel's vertical deformation, two
 533 sequential damage states were introduced as listed in Table 12. The fragility curves
 534 considered for categories CL1 and CL2 are shown in Figure 17.

535 **Table 12.** Vertical pressure vessel: Damage state classification and associated EDPs.

DS	Attainment of DS when	EDP
ds0	—	—
ds1	First leakage (minor damage to vessel's components)	Rotation of piping and force on base connection
ds2	Complete release of content (failure of piping) and global collapse of vessel (failure of anchorage)	Rotation of piping and force on base connection

536
 537 **Figure 17.** Vertical pressure vessel of type CL1 and CL2: Empirical-CDF fragility.

538 The failure of horizontal vessels is attributed to the failure of their anchorage, as has
 539 been confirmed by several observations made in the aftermath of past earthquake events
 540 (Johnson et al., 2000; Roche et al., 1995). Thus, the seismic performance analysis was
 541 carried out separately for the longitudinal and the transverse direction of the anchorage
 542 concerning the longitudinal axis of the vessel. The anchorage consists of different bolt
 543 configurations connecting the saddle to the foundation, with the latter being typically a rigid
 544 RC block on the ground level or RC sleepers. Two sequential damage states were

545 introduced related to the performance of the connected piping and the foundation capacity.
 546 The damage state classification along with the associated LS definitions are listed in Table
 547 13. The fragility curves considered for the longitudinal and the transverse directions are
 548 shown in Figure 18 for $AvgS_a$.

549 **Table 13.** Horizontal pressure vessel: Damage state classification and associated EDPs.

DS	Attainment of DS when	EDP
ds0	—	—
ds1	First leakage (minor damage to piping) and minor damage to the vessel's structural system	Rotation of piping, base connection, and foundation capacity
ds2	Complete release of content (failure of piping) and global collapse of vessel (failure of anchorage)	Rotation of piping, base connection, and foundation capacity

550
 551 **Figure 18.** Horizontal pressure vessel: Empirical-CDF fragility curves in the transverse and
 552 longitudinal directions.

553 HOMOGENIZATION OF DAMAGE STATES

554 Damage states have been identified for each structure separately to examine their
 555 susceptibility to damage. However, the failure (either operational or structural) of each asset
 556 does not have the same level of impact on the overall operational integrity of the refinery.
 557 It is thus useful to homogenize the asset-level damage states (ds) to a set of refinery-level
 558 damage states (DS) that better denote their functionality consequences. The latter can be
 559 denoted as global DSs and range from 'none' to 'severe' disruption. The five distinct global
 560 DSs are colored after ATC-20 (Applied Technology Council, 1989) and are shown in
 561 Figure 19. It is noted that the use of uppercase and lowercase letters for the damage states
 562 only serves to distinguish the refinery- and asset-level damage states, respectively.

563 The homogenization of DSs is offered in Table 14 taking into account the following
 564 aspects: (1) the importance of each asset in the refining process, (2) the consequences of
 565 potential business disruption (downtime and cost) for the entire refinery, (3) the location of
 566 the asset, (4) the potential cascading effects due to a failure and the spread of damage due

567 to loss of containment and subsequent fires, and (5) expert opinion. It should be noted that
 568 due to the significant operational interaction between the assets and the complexity of the
 569 refining process, the failure of a single asset will have an impact on the refinery's
 570 functionality, the magnitude of which depends on a complex combination of factors that
 571 cannot be quantified herein.

Damage State	DS0	DS1	DS2	DS3	DS4
Level of disruption	None	Low	Moderate	Extensive	Severe
Operational status	—	Refinery is operational at almost 100% capacity	Refinery is operational with some parts at reduced capacity	Refinery is partially operational at reduced capacity	Refinery is partially operational at low capacity and may be shut down
Repairs required	—	Some assets require scheduling of minor repairs	Some assets require immediate major repairs	Some assets require extensive repairs	Many assets require extensive repairs and/or replacement

572

573 **Figure 19.** Global damage states in terms of operational disruption at the refinery level

574 To offer a deeper understanding of this process, two indicative examples are provided:

- 575 • In case a steel chimney fails due to local buckling of the shell (asset-level ds3), the
 576 consequences to the refinery would be similarly extensive (refinery-level DS3), as the
 577 gaseous waste can not be released safely. Thus, the part of the refinery that is served by
 578 said chimney needs to cease operations. Note that different chimneys may serve different
 579 parts, hence the disruption is somewhat contained. Contrarily, the failure of a steel
 580 process tower due to shell local buckling (asset-level ds2) causes a severe functionality
 581 reduction (refinery-level DS4) due to this typically being an asset with little-to-no
 582 redundancy (for the size of this refinery). Thus, it will directly disrupt the refining
 583 process chain, leading to extreme business disruption and downtime until repairs take
 584 place.
- 585 • In case a vertical or horizontal pressure vessel fails (asset-level ds2), the consequences
 586 to the refinery can be considered to be moderate, as different/spare vessels can be
 587 employed temporarily. In contrast, the failure of a spherical pressure vessel (asset-level
 588 ds3) would have devastating consequences for the entire refinery (severe functionality
 589 disruption), considering also the increased potential for fire, explosion, and
 590 environmental pollution.

591 Taking advantage of the homogenization of damage states, it is useful to perform a
 592 preliminary qualitative identification of the assets that can contribute most to the disruption

593 of refinery business. To do so, the fragility curves of assets for global DS1 and DS4,
 594 indicatively, are shown in Figure 20 and Figure 21, respectively.

595
 596 **Figure 20.** Global DS1: Fragility curves of assets.

597
 598 **Figure 21.** Global DS4: Fragility curves of assets.

Table 14. Homogenization of damage states in terms of operational disruption

Structure	DS0 None	DS1 Low disruption	DS2 Moderate	DS3 Extensive	DS4 Severe
Unanchored liquid storage tank	—	ds1: Damage to upper shell course	ds2: Damage to upper shell course or base plate failure		ds3: Exceedance of elephant's foot buckling or base plate failure
Anchored liquid storage tank	—	ds1: Damage to upper shell course or anchorage bolt yielding	ds2: Damage to upper shell course or anchorage bolt fracture or base plate failure		ds3: Exceedance of elephant's foot buckling or base plate failure
Buildings	—	ds1: Anchorage failure of at least one component in IC I	ds2: Anchorage failure of at least one component in IC II	ds3: Anchorage failure of at least one component in IC III	
Process tower	—		ds1: Damage to connected piping		ds2: Local buckling of shell
Steel chimney	—	ds1: Damage to connected piping	ds2: Damage to liner	ds3: Local buckling of shell	
RC chimney	—	ds1: Damage to connected piping	ds2: Damage to liner or cross-section yielding	ds3: Cross-section failure	
Flare	—		ds1: Damage to equipment	ds2: Damage to vertical piping	ds3: Tensile or buckling structural member failure
Spherical pressure vessel	—		ds1: First yielding of any brace in tension	ds2: Yielding of more than 50% of braces in tension	ds3: Fracture of any brace
Vertical pressure vessel	—	ds1: Minor damage of vessel's components	ds2: Failure of piping and global collapse of vessel		
Horizontal pressure vessel	—	ds1: Minor damage to piping and structure	ds2: Failure of piping and anchorage		

600 purposes, taken as relatively empty ($FR = 0.35$), half-full ($FR = 0.65$), and almost full
601 ($FR = 0.95$). The same fill ratios are considered and presented for the spherical pressure
602 vessel. By inspecting the fragilities, it can be seen that: (i) there is significant variability
603 among the assets due to the inherent different dynamic and structural properties; (ii) almost
604 full liquid storage tanks and spherical vessels are more susceptible to seismic-induced
605 damage; (iii) the potential failure of pressure vessels or the anchorage of acceleration-
606 sensitive equipment nested in buildings or a tall chimney has higher probability to cause
607 low functionality disruption (DS1), compared to other structures; (iv) liquid storage tanks
608 that are filled above half of their storage capacity may contribute significantly to severe
609 functionality disruption in comparison to other high-rise stacks or spherical vessels. At this
610 point, it should be noted that the comparison of fragilities offers a preliminary estimation
611 of which asset may fail “first” in case of an earthquake and affect the operation of the
612 refinery. Furthermore, what is critical for the stakeholders is a reliable connection between
613 structural damages and physical consequences (e.g., material release, fire, explosion) in a
614 quantitative manner (Alessandri et al., 2018; Fabbrocino et al., 2005), which is presently
615 out of our scope.

616 REPOSITORY

617 The data repository is available by Melissianos et al. (2024) at
618 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11419659> The repository contains separate folders that
619 contain (a) the seismological data, namely the selected ground motion records and the
620 modified ESHM13 seismological model, (b) the exposure model, and (c) the database
621 related to the refinery assets examined structured in folders per structural type, namely
622 Liquid Storage Tanks, Buildings, Pressure Vessels, and High-Rise Stacks. In each folder, a
623 single spreadsheet contains all the information in separate sheets. In more detail: (i) The
624 “Introduction” sheet presents the structure, the nomenclature used, and the contents of the
625 spreadsheet; (ii) the “1. Structure” sheet shows the geometry of the asset along with an
626 overview of the developed numerical model; (iii) the “2. Modal_Analysis” sheet presents
627 the results of the structure’s modal analysis in terms of eigenmodes, eigenperiods, and
628 damping ratios, (iv) the “3. Damage_States” sheet shows the considered damage states,
629 along with the EDP and the corresponding capacity checks, (v) the “4.1.*. IDA_PGA_**”
630 and “4.2.*. IDA_AvgSa_**” sheets list the IDA results from both IMs (PGA and $AvgS_a$)
631 considered per EDP (* denotes the number of the EDP and ** denotes its name); (5) the
632 “5.1. Fragility_PGA” and “5.2. Fragility_AvgSa” sheets present the calculated empirical-

633 CDF fragilities, which are also plotted for illustration purposes in the “5.3. Fragility_Plots”
634 sheet.

635

CONCLUSIONS

636 In support of seismic risk and resilience assessment of industrial facilities and NaTech
637 events, we present the VASEL virtual testbed, resembling a realistic mid-size refinery in
638 high-seismicity Mediterranean regions. It comprises a full exposure model with site seismic
639 hazard and fragility definition of the critical refinery assets. Critical details for the location
640 and function of each structure are provided, offering earthquake and risk engineers an
641 insight into the facility's operation and how the operational interdependencies of the assets
642 affect the risk estimation process.

643 The critical assets at risk are identified and analyzed via appropriate simplified
644 (reduced-order or surrogate) models that can capture the main failure modes associated with
645 functionality disruption and structural damage. High-fidelity fragility curves are produced
646 to identify each asset's susceptibility to business interruption or structural damage for
647 various levels of seismic intensity. Moreover, critical issues associated with these assets are
648 detailed and demonstrated, such as the importance of equipment supported in building-type
649 structures, how this affects the fragility of the structure, and the effect of the fill ratio in
650 liquid and gas storage tanks. The homogenization of damages states is presented to
651 showcase the transition from the asset to the refinery level to assess the potential of refinery
652 functionality disruption and associated NaTech events. Finally, a modern refinery remains
653 a complex petrochemical facility for which we have only provided structural information
654 on critical assets. Piping, water, steam, power, and transportation infrastructure, as well as
655 their interconnectivity with the described assets, are required to form a complete picture of
656 the refinery, even in its virtual testbed form.

657

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661

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677

RESEARCH DATA AND CODE AVAILABILITY

678 The open-source data presented in this paper is available at Melissianos et al. (2024).
679 [Reference in list: Melissianos, V. E., Kareferis, N. D., Bakalis, K., Kazantzi, A. K., and
680 Vamvatsikos, D., 2024. Exposure and fragility of a virtual oil refinery testbed for seismic
681 risk assessment. Zenodo repository. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11419659>]. No
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683

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